

Supplementary Materials: Behavioral strategies of prehistoric and historic children from dental microwear texture analysis

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Statistical analyses

Table S4: Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric tests

Microwear variable	Test Statistic	df	<i>p</i>
<i>epLsar</i>	12.643	3	0.005
<i>Asfc</i>	12.604	3	0.006
<i>Smc</i>	12.441	3	0.006
<i>HAsfc₉</i>	12.620	3	0.006
<i>HAsfc₈₁</i>	12.611	3	0.006